

Environmental Noise Directive Reporting guidelines

DF2 Competent Authorities

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Summary

The reporting guidelines are intended to support reporters that will be conducting the submission of data required under the Environmental Noise Directive. The document provides an overview to the reporting process in Reportnet 3.0 and it describes the quality checks that are undertaken during the submission process. In addition to this, reporting examples are also provided. A key goal of this document is to ensure a common understanding among data providers working on the implementation of the Environmental Noise Directive. This document should further be of assistance to both thematic and IT experts.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This document aims to provide detailed guidance on the practicalities and processes for reporting environmental noise data to Reportnet 3.0, the central hub from which all e-Reporting activities handled by the EEA with Eionet and other partners will be performed.

In this context, a user is assumed to be a representative of an EU Member State or other reporting country who is submitting relevant country-level noise data to Reportnet 3.0.

These reporting guidelines are intended to support reporting countries in providing high quality noise reports in an efficient manner following the new Implementing Decision on *Setting up a mandatory data repository and a mandatory digital information exchange mechanism according to Directive 2002/49/EC*.

Specifically, this document is focused on the reporting of DF2 Competent Authorities and covers:

- The legal basis of the END requirements addressed in the Implementing Decision on Setting up a mandatory data repository and a mandatory digital information exchange mechanism according to Directive 2002/49/EC
- The technical requirements for the data submission
- The structure of Reportnet 3.0 in relation to this dataflow
- The practicalities involved in reporting and submitting data using Reportnet 3.0

These reporting guidelines are intended to be a stand-alone document that contains all necessary information for reporting. However, other documents and video recordings may offer additional detail on certain aspects and are available in the webpage: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise>.

1.2 The legal basis

Reporting noise data under the Environmental Noise Directive (END) will occur in Reportnet 3.0 from 2022. The END reporting is defined in the Directive 2002/49/EC and the reporting requirements are further defined in the *Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/1967 of 11 November 2021 on Setting up a mandatory data repository and a mandatory digital information exchange mechanism according to Directive 2002/49/EC*¹. The current reporting obligations of the Environmental Noise Directive have been adapted to also fulfil the new INSPIRE directive which is based on the harmonisation and sharing of spatial data and infrastructures based on the 2019 regulation² which amends different articles of the END. Firstly, the regulation obliges countries to produce *noise maps and action plans according to the Inspire Directive* and secondly, it obliges the EC and the EEA to

¹ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/1967 of 11 November 2021 setting up a mandatory data repository and a mandatory digital information exchange mechanism in accordance with Directive 2002/49/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (Text with EEA relevance) C/2021/7948 ELI: http://data.europa.eu/eli/dec_impl/2021/1967/oj

² Regulation (EU) 2019/1010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the alignment of reporting obligations in the field of legislation related to the environment, and amending Regulations (EC) No 166/2006 and (EU) No 995/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Directives 2002/49/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2007/2/EC, 2009/147/EC and 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 338/97 and (EC) No 2173/2005, and Council Directive 86/278/EEC (Text with EEA relevance). ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1010/oj>

develop a *mandatory digital information exchange mechanism* that countries have to use to report and share the data under the END directive. Therefore, the use of the Reportnet 3.0 platform and the use of data that is INSPIRE compliant will be mandatory for the reporting of data under the END. In order to support countries in their reporting obligations, we developed new templates and a new Reporting system that fulfils both the END and the INSPIRE requirements.

Figure 1.1. Overview on new noise reporting mechanism

1.3 Alignment with the INSPIRE Directive

The alignment between the Environmental Noise Directive and the INSPIRE Directive has been included throughout the development process of establishing the mandatory digital information exchange mechanism.

Based on the legal basis, explained in the section above (1.2), the END conceptual data model has been developed on the basis of the INSPIRE conceptual data models for spatial data themes by combining specific END reporting requirements and INSPIRE requirements.

The parts of the END conceptual data model which don't include spatial data still incorporate relevant generic INSPIRE principles and requirements such as thematic identifiers, common data types and use of code lists. This is relevant for the END data flows of DF2, DF3, DF6_9 and the descriptive parts of noise action plans in DF7_10.

The flexibility of the reporting infrastructure Reportnet 3.0 allows providing reported data into infrastructure in different ways, from importing files, programmatically by configuring the Reportnet 3.0 API, or in the future by harvesting INSPIRE services for spatial data.

Figure 1.2. Overview on the integration of INSPIRE directive into noise reporting obligations

2 Understanding the new END data model

The structure and details of the data model are described in the *Data model documentation* and can be accessed at <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/data-model-documentation>.

In order to develop the data model for Competent Authority (DF2) we considered the following:

- the END requirements;
- INSPIRE principles and identifiers: some data types are according to INSPIRE and identifiers

The data model described in the data model documentation is used for several interrelated purposes:

- It is used for presenting the content of the noise data that needs to be reported.
- It is used to develop the encoding templates in MS Excel
- It is used to design the schemas in Reportnet 3.0 that will be used for data reporting.

The relevant section of the Data model documentation for the reporting of dataflow DF2 is section 11.

3 Understanding the basic principles of Reportnet 3.0 from a reporter point of view

The Regulation (EU) 2019/1010 on the alignment of reporting obligations in the field of legislation related to the environment and the implementing decision on setting up a mandatory data repository and a mandatory digital information exchange mechanism according to Directive 2002/49/EC, specifies that a digital information exchange mechanism should be used for reporting on all dimensions of the Environmental Noise Directive (END) by Member States.

A key element of the new reporting system, Reportnet 3.0 is being developed by the European Environment Agency. Reportnet 3.0 (<https://reportnet.europa.eu/>) is the next generation platform for reporting environmental data to the EEA and also host several reporting tasks for the European Commission. Reportnet 3.0 is a centralized e-Reporting platform, aiming at simplifying and streamlining the data flow steps across all environmental domains. The system acts as a one-stop-shop for all involved stakeholders.

Important links

- Reportnet 3 reporters' manual : https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/prod/reporter_howto_reportnet3.0
- Training videos: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/videos>

Once the reporter is successfully logged-in in Reportnet 3.0, the dataflows assigned to the reporter will show up as illustrated in Figure 3.1. In Reportnet 3.0, the reporter is able to see the list of dataflows along with information related to the role, the delivery date, the dataflow name, the dataflow description, the associated obligation and instrument, the status of the reporting obligation.

Figure 3.1. Dataflows overview: main page and list of dataflows assigned to the reporter

Figure 3.2 shows the general structure of the dataflow view. Figure 3.3 shows more specifically the reporting window of the dataflow *Competent Authority (DF2)*.

Figure 3.2. Reportnet – Reporter view: general dataflow structure

Figure 3.3. Reportnet – Reporter view: general dataflow structure for the END Competent Authority (DF2) reporting

The dataflow is organised by schemas. In *Competent Authority (DF2)* there is one data schema to report the designated competent authority and bodies responsible for implementing the Directive 2002/49/EC.

There is another data schema called *Reference dataset - Vocabulary – Common tables*. This is a read-only schema and contains the different code list that are applicable to this dataflow as well as several tables that are used for data validation (see Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4. Reference dataset - Vocabulary – Common tables for Competent Authority (DF2)

Validations	Notation	Label	Definition	URI
	agglomerationAir	Aircraft noise inside agglomeration	Related to air traffic inside the boundary of the agglomeration, including major airports and other airports. Applicable to data flows: Agglomeration Source (DF1_S), Competent Authority (DF2), Noise Limit Value (DF3), Strategic Noise Map - Noise Exposure (DF4_B), Noise Action Plan Agglomeration (DF7_10), Quiet Area (DF7_10)	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue/agglomerationAir
	agglomerationIndustry	Industrial noise inside agglomeration	Related to industrial sites inside the boundary of the agglomeration. Applicable to data flows: Agglomeration Source (DF1_S), Competent Authority (DF2), Noise Limit Value (DF3), Strategic Noise Map - Noise Exposure (DF4_B), Noise Action Plan Agglomeration (DF7_10), Quiet Area (DF7_10)	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue/agglomerationIndustry
	agglomerationMajorAirport	Noise from major airports inside agglomeration	Related to major airports inside the boundary of the agglomeration. Applicable to data flows: Agglomeration Source (DF1_S), Competent Authority (DF2), Strategic Noise Map - Noise Exposure (DF4_B), Noise Action Plan Agglomeration (DF7_10)	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue/agglomerationMajorAirport

Finally, the *Dataflow Help* contains relevant help documents, including the MS Excel template, the links to all supporting materials, all the information on quality controls and validation rules, as well as the description of the different tables and attributes applicable to this dataflow (see Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5. Dataflow help page: supporting documents tab, web links tab and dataset schemas tab

Title	Description	Category	Language	Public	Upload date	Size	File
Competent Authority (DF2).xlsx	Competent Authority (DF2) template	xlsx	English	✓	2021-12-07	18.12 KB	

If the system doesn't react click refresh/reload page

If problems with Reportnet 3.0 persist please contact helpdesk@reportnet.europa.eu

3.1 Validation

The following level error types have been implemented in Reportnet 3.0.:

- BLOCKER: Blocker messages indicate that the detected error will prevent data submission (data release is not possible).
- ERROR: Error messages indicate issues that clearly need corrective action by the data reporter.

- **WARNING:** Warning messages indicate issues that may be an error. Data reporters are expected to double-check relevant records.
- **INFO:** Informative message. Neutral or statistical feedback about the delivery, e.g. number of species reported.

The applicable validations and error types into the data schema of *Competent Authority (DF2)* dataflow are outlined in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Applicable validation levels in the schema of Competent Authority (DF2) dataflow

	Competent Authority (DF2)
Applicable validation level	Blocker Error Warning Info

The validations (quality control - QC) are documented in the Reportnet 3 Data Flow Help schema.

Figure 3.6. Dataflow help – Details of the data schemas and applied validations

Additionally, a copy of validations applicable to the Competent Authority (DF2) dataflow is published in the Noise Eionet Portal for public consideration. Please note that the original information is always in the Reportnet 3 platform.

The detailed validations applicable to the Competent Authority (DF2) dataflow can be consulted in: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/validation-rules/>

Validations need to be run for each data schema. In each schema, data can be validated by clicking on “Validate” (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7. Validation of the data being loaded

Once the validation has been performed a notification will pop up on the top-right hand of the screen. After clicking “Refresh”, errors, if any, will be displayed at four types:

- Field error
- Record error
- Table error
- Dataset error

The column “Validations” shows for each record which level of errors at field and record level can be found.

Finally, the button “Show validations” in the dataset menu (Figure 3.8) shows the list of all errors in the dataset, displayed in a summary table grouped by a particular error type (more information can be found in https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/prod/reporter_howto_reportnet3.0).

Figure 3.8. Show validations function in the dataset menu

A BLOCKER in the dataflow will prevent the reporter to officially submit any data in Reportnet 3.0.

4 Key concepts in relation to *Competent Authority (DF2)*

4.1 Reporting data schema structure for DF2

The data schema developed in Reportnet 3.0 are based on the specific UML diagram illustrated in the *END Data model documentation* (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/data-model-documentation>). The MS Excel template follow the same schemas and principles as the UML diagram.

Figure 4.1. Data schemas for *Competent Authority (DF2)* delivery in Reportnet 3.0

4.2 Identifiers

4.2.1 Thematic identifiers

The concept of thematic identifiers is re-used in the END reporting scope from the INSPIRE data specifications. Thematic identifiers may have been established to meet data exchange requirements within thematic domains, e.g. different reporting obligations at International, European or national levels, and/or internal data maintenance requirements. A property that is considered a thematic identifier will use data type **ThematicIdentifier** which is composed of two mandatory parts:

- **identifier**: Unique identifier used to identify the spatial object within the specified identification scheme;
- **identifierScheme**: Identifier defining the scheme used to assign the identifier.

This concept of thematic identifiers and data type **ThematicIdentifier** are re-used across the complete END data model to uniquely identify spatial objects and all other objects – entities, e.g.: major road segments, major railway segments, agglomerations, competent authorities, quiet areas, reports of limit values, noise control programmes and noise action plans. The internationally defined ICAO code for airports is also used as a thematic identifier.

The guidelines “Proposal on how to build the unique thematic identifiers for the new END data model” provides detailed information and coding system to create thematic identifiers. (See more information in: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/guidelines/codes_formation_doc.pdf/view).

4.2.2 Providing thematic identifiers in the END reported data

Identifier scheme EUENDCode

The unique identifier scheme with the name **EUENDCode** is defined for the END reporting scope. It is published in the Eionet Data Dictionary as <http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/inspire/IdentifierScheme/EUENDCode>.

It is used across the END reporting data flows and reporting data as the default value and it is stored (pre-filled) in the table DatasetDefaultProperties. This table is included in the pre-defined data templates in GeoPackage (spatial data) and in the Reportnet 3.0 data schemas.

To make data preparation easier, the table DatasetDefaultProperties is pre-filled with all applicable default values in the reporting data flow, therefore it doesn't require any changes.

4.2.3 Re-using object identifiers defined in data flow DF1_5 for data flow DF2

Data flow DF2 re-uses object identifiers of agglomerations, major airports, major roads and major railways that have been defined in the data flow DF1_5.

The only value required to be provided for each object is “identifier”.

The data schema Competent Authority (DF2) includes object identifiers in the following way:

- The field `agglomerationIdIdentifier` will be used for identifier of an agglomeration;
- The field `roadIdIdentifier` will be used for identifier of a road segment;
- The field `railIdIdentifier` will be used for identifier of a railway segment;
- The field `ICAOCode` will be used for identifier of an airport (ICAO code to be provided).

4.3 From conceptual data model (UML) to MS Excel templates

MS Excel templates based on the conceptual data model (UML) have been created to support data reporting. The templates can be found in the Dataflow Help page in Reportnet 3.0.

Figure 4.2. Screenshot of the Dataflow help page where the MS Excel template is available for download

The screenshot shows the 'Dataflow help' page for 'Competent authority (DF2): REPORTNET TEST'. It features a table with columns for Title, Description, Category, Language, Public, Upload date, Size, and File. A single row is visible, representing the MS Excel template.

Title	Description	Category	Language	Public	Upload date	Size	File
Competent Authority (DF2).xlsx	Competent Authority (DF2) template	xlsx	English	✓	2021-12-07	18.12 KB	

MS Excel template can be downloaded from:
<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise>

5 Data schema: Competent Authority (DF2)

5.1 Description

Information about the designated competent authority and bodies responsible for implementing the Directive 2002/49/EC, including the authorities responsible for: making and, where relevant, approving noise maps and action plans for agglomerations, major roads, major railways, and major airports; collecting noise maps and action plans; and, optionally, for designating quiet areas.

The Competent Authority data schema includes 9 tables:

- CompetentAuthorityDetails
- CompetentAuthorityAirport
- CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration
- CompetentAuthorityRail
- CompetentAuthorityRoad
- CompetentAuthorityQuietArea
- ESTATUnitReference
- DatasetDefaultProperties: Information about the default values of objects in a data set or a table (read only schema, and already filled in in Reportnet 3.0)
- CodelistProperties: list of applicable code lists in that data schema (read only schema, and already filled in in Reportnet 3.0).

5.2 Table CompetentAuthorityDetails

The table *CompetentAuthorityDetails* provides information about the competent authority and bodies responsible for implementing the END Directive.

Table 5.1.C CompetentAuthorityDetails table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
M	competentAuthorityId_identifier	Text	
M	competentAuthorityName	Text	
M	streetName	Text	
M	buildingName	Text	
M	postalCode	Text	
M	city	Text	

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.2.1 *Field competentAuthorityId_identifier*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	The value of this field will be reused across the different tables in this schema
Example	CA_CZ_00_10

5.2.2 *Field competentAuthorityName*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Full name of the competent authority responsible for implementing the END Directive, that can include the Organisation name, Department and Unit (if applicable)
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	Air Pollution, Environment and Health Group

5.2.3 *Field streetName*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Street name as part of the competent authority's official address
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	Kongens Nytorv

5.2.4 *Field buildingNumber*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Number of the building as part of the competent authority's official address
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	6

5.2.5 Field postalCode

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Postal code of the city where the competent authority is located. It is part of the competent authority's official address
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	1050

5.2.6 Field city

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Name of the city where the competent authority is located. It is part of the competent authority's official address
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	Copenhagen

5.3 Table CompetentAuthorityAirport

The table *CompetentAuthorityAirport* provides information about responsibilities of the competent authority or its organisational units with regard to developing, approving or collecting noise maps and action plans related to noise from major airports. Responsibilities of competent authority or its organisational units shall be provided for each major airport.

Table 5.2. *CompetentAuthorityAirport* table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
M	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	Text	
M	ICAOCode	Text	
M	competentAuthorityRole	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.3.1 Field *competentAuthorityIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the data type <i>CompetentAuthorityDetails</i> (<i>competentAuthorityId_identifier</i>).
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	CA_CZ_00_10

5.3.2 Field *ICAOCode*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique international code of airport defined by the International Civil Aviation Organization.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	ICAO codes provided need to be coincident with the information provided in DF1_5, DF4_8 and DF7_10
Example	LOWW
Reporting constraints	Responsibilities of competent authority or its organisational units shall be provided for each major airport

5.3.3 Field *competentAuthorityRole*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Role of the competent authority for major airport
Reportnet type	3.0 Link
Format	Multiple values are allowed Value separated list with the separation character “;” (semicolon)
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mappingDevelopment - mappingApproval (only if applicable) - mappingCollection - actionPlanDevelopment - actionPlanApproval (only if applicable) - actionPlanCollection
Information	The code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” are mandatory and need to be provided per each ICAOCode. Code values “mappingApproval” and “actionPlanApproval” are optional.
Example	mappingDevelopment; actionPlanDevelopment; actionPlanCollection
Reporting constraints	Submission of DF2 will be blocked if the information on competent authorities is not provided for the code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” per entity reported.

5.4 Table *CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration*

The table *CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration* provides information about responsibilities of the competent authority or its organisational units with regard to developing, approving or collecting noise maps and action plans related to noise in agglomerations. Responsibilities of competent authority or its organisational units shall be provided for each agglomeration.

Table 5.3. *CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration* table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
M	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	Text	
M	agglomerationIdIdentifier	Text	
M	competentAuthoritySource	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue/
M	competentAuthorityRole	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.4.1 Field *competentAuthorityIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the data type <i>CompetentAuthorityDetails</i> (<i>competentAuthorityId_identifier</i>).
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	CA_DE_BW_10

5.4.2 Field *agglomerationIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier assigned to each agglomeration. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the feature type <i>AgglomerationSource</i> (<i>agglomerationId_identifier</i>) from END dataflow DF1_5 for Agglomerations.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	The value of this field re-uses the identifier of the agglomerations defined in DF1_5 (see more information in section 4.2.3). <i>agglomerationIdIdentifier</i> provided need to be coincident with the information provided in DF1_5, DF4_8 and DF7_10.
Example	AG_DE_BW_3
Reporting constraints	Agglomeration identifier will be re-used across the complete END data model to uniquely identify spatial objects and all other objects – entities. Each unique identifier provided in this dataflow should be provided in Noise Sources (DF1_5) dataflow.

5.4.3 Field competentAuthoritySource

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Noise source for which the competent authority is responsible inside agglomeration
Reportnet 3.0 type	Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	<p>Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue/</p> <p>Applicable code list values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conditional: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ agglomerationAir (if applicable) ○ agglomerationIndustry (if applicable) ○ agglomerationRoad (if applicable) ○ agglomerationRailway (if applicable) ○ OR ○ agglomerationAllSources - Optional: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ agglomerationMajorAirport ○ agglomerationMajorRoad ○ agglomerationMajorRailway
Information	<p>Cities need to provide the competent authorities responsible for the END implementation for the different noise sources existing inside each agglomeration.</p> <p>For instance, cities that have roads and railways but no airports are expected to select “agglomerationRoad”, “agglomerationRailway”, “agglomerationMajorRoad”, “agglomerationMajorRailway” and provide the competent authority in relation to each noise source inside the agglomeration.</p> <p>“agglomerationAllSources” can also be selected if only one competent authority is responsible for the END implementation in the agglomeration for the applicable sources declared in DF1_5.</p>
Example	agglomerationRoad
Reporting constraints	<p>Competent authorities to the different noise sources reported here will be compared with the “applicableSource” reported in Agglomeration Source (DF1_5) schema of the Noise Sources (DF1_5) data flow. All noise sources declared in DF1_5 “applicableSource” must be provided in competent authorities for agglomerations.</p> <p>By selecting the code list “agglomerationAllSources”, it is going to be assumed that the competent authority is responsible for the implementation of the END for all the noise sources declared in DF1_5 “applicableSource”.</p>

5.4.4 Field *competentAuthorityRole*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Role of the competent authority with regard to the selected noise source inside agglomeration
Reportnet type	3.0 Link
Format	Multiple values are allowed Value separated list with the separation character “;” (semicolon)
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mappingDevelopment - mappingApproval (only if applicable) - mappingCollection - actionPlanDevelopment - actionPlanApproval (only if applicable) - actionPlanCollection
Information	The code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” are mandatory and need to be provided per each “agglomerationIdIdentifier” and “competentAuthoritySource”. Code values “mappingApproval” and “actionPlanApproval” are optional.
Example	mappingDevelopment; actionPlanDevelopment; actionPlanCollection
Reporting constraints	Submission of DF2 will be blocked if the information on competent authorities is not provided for the code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” per entity reported.

5.5 Table *CompetentAuthorityRail*

The table *CompetentAuthorityRail* provides information about responsibilities of the competent authority or its organisational units with regard to developing, approving or collecting noise maps and action plans related to noise from major railways. Responsibilities of competent authority or its organisational units shall be provided for major railway segments.

Table 5.4. CompetentAuthorityRail table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
M	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	Text	
M	competentAuthorityRole	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
M	reportingLevel	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/LevelValue
C	ESTATUnitCode	Text	
C	railIdIdentifier	Text	

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.5.1 Field competentAuthorityIdIdentifier

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the data type CompetentAuthorityDetails (competentAuthorityId_identifier).
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	CA_AT_00_7

5.5.2 Field *competentAuthorityRole*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Role of the competent authority for major railway
Reportnet type	3.0 Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mappingDevelopment - mappingApproval (only if applicable) - mappingCollection - actionPlanDevelopment - actionPlanApproval (only if applicable) - actionPlanCollection
Information	The code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” are mandatory and need to be provided per each unique combination between “reportingLevel” and the corresponding “ESTATUnitCode” or “railIdIdentifier” . Code values “mappingApproval” and “actionPlanApproval” are optional.
Example	actionPlanDevelopment
Reporting constraints	Submission of DF2 will be blocked if the information on competent authorities is not provided for the code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection”.

5.5.3 Field *reportingLevel*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Reporting level of the competent authorities for major railway. Country, NUTS 1, NUTS 2, NUTS 3, LAU or entity (representing segments of major railways) should be provided.
Reportnet type	3.0 Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/ReportingLevelValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entity - LAU - NUTS3 - NUTS2 - NUTS1 - country
Example	LAU

5.5.4 Field *ESTATUnitCode*

Requirement	Conditional
Description	Unique identifier assigned to each ESTAT Unit corresponding to the reporting unit chosen, according to Eurostat classification of territorial units. Shall be reported if country, NUTS or LAU are selected in reportingLevel attribute.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	LAU code to be reported when selecting LAU code value in the attribute "reportingLevel". NUTS1, NUTS 2, NUTS3 code to be reported when selecting NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3 code values respectively in the attribute "reportingLevel". Country code to be reported when selecting country code value in the attribute "reportingLevel".
Example	50101
Reporting constraints	If NUTS or LAU are provided, the table ESTATUnitReference should be filled in.

5.5.5 Field *railIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Conditional
Description	Unique code corresponding to a railway segment comprised within the territorial unit code. The unique code is expected to be the same as the identifier from the feature type MajorRailwaySource (railId_identifier) from END dataflow DF1_5 for Major Railways.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	The segment must be split according to the territorial unit chosen in reportingLevel. The value of this field re-uses the identifier of the major railways defined in DF1_5 (see more information in section 4.2.3).
Example	RL_AT_00_1
Reporting constraints	railId_identifier to be reported when selecting "entity" in the attribute "reportingLevel".

5.6 Table *CompetentAuthorityRoad*

The table *CompetentAuthorityRoad* provides information about responsibilities of the competent authority or its organisational units with regard to developing, approving or collecting noise maps and action plans related to noise from major roads. Responsibilities of competent authority or its organisational units shall be provided for major roads segments.

Table 5.5. CompetentAuthorityRoad table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
M	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	Text	
M	competentAuthorityRole	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
M	reportingLevel	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/LevelValue
C	ESTATUnitCode	Text	
C	roadIdIdentifier	Text	

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.6.1 Field competentAuthorityIdIdentifier

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the data type CompetentAuthorityDetails (competentAuthorityId_identifier).
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	CA_AT_00_7

5.6.2 Field *competentAuthorityRole*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Role of the competent authority for major roads
Reportnet 3.0 type	Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mappingDevelopment - mappingApproval (only if applicable) - mappingCollection - actionPlanDevelopment - actionPlanApproval (only if applicable) - actionPlanCollection
Information	The code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection” are mandatory and need to be provided per each unique combination between “reportingLevel” and the corresponding “ESTATUnitCode” or “roadIdIdentifier” . Code values “mappingApproval” and “actionPlanApproval” are optional.
Example	actionPlanDevelopment; actionPlanCollection
Reporting constraints	Submission of DF2 will be blocked if the information on competent authorities is not provided for the code values “mappingDevelopment”, “mappingCollection”, “actionPlanDevelopment” and “actionPlanCollection”.

5.6.3 Field *reportingLevel*

Requirement	Mandatory
Description	Reporting level of the competent authorities for major road. Country, NUTS 1, NUTS 2, NUTS 3, LAU or entity (representing segments of major roads) should be provided.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/ReportingLevelValue Applicable code list values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entity - LAU - NUTS3 - NUTS2 - NUTS1 - country
Example	LAU

5.6.4 Field *ESTATUnitCode*

Requirement	Conditional
Description	Unique identifier assigned to each ESTAT Unit corresponding to the reporting unit chosen, according to Eurostat classification of territorial units. Shall be reported if country, NUTS or LAU are selected in reportingLevel attribute.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	LAU code to be reported when selecting LAU code value in the attribute "reportingLevel". NUTS1, NUTS 2, NUTS3 code to be reported when selecting NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3 code values respectively in the attribute "reportingLevel". Country code to be reported when selecting country code value in the attribute "reportingLevel".
Example	50101
Reporting constraints	If NUTS or LAU are provided, the table <i>ESTATUnitReference</i> should be filled in.

5.6.5 Field *roadIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Conditional
Description	Unique code corresponding to a road segment comprised within the territorial unit code. The unique code is expected to be the same as the identifier from the feature type <i>MajorRoadSource</i> (<i>roadId_identifier</i>) from END dataflow <i>DF1_5</i> for Major Roads.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	The segment must be split according to the territorial unit chosen in reportingLevel. The value of this field re-uses the identifier of the major roads defined in <i>DF1_5</i> (see more information in section 4.2.3).
Example	RD_AT_00_1
Reporting constraints	<i>roadId_identifier</i> to be reported when selecting "entity" in the attribute "reportingLevel".

5.7 Table *CompetentAuthorityQuietArea*

The table *CompetentAuthorityQuietArea* provides information about the competent authority or its organisational units with regard to designation of quiet areas (both inside agglomerations and in open country).

This table and other information related to quiet areas must be provided when quiet areas are delimited inside agglomerations or in open country. If no quiet area is delimited, no information shall be reported.

Table 5.6. *CompetentAuthorityQuietArea* table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
O	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	Text	
O	competentAuthorityType	Link	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/inspire/SpecialisedZoneTypeCode
O	quietAreaIdIdentifier	Text	

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.7.1 Field *competentAuthorityIdIdentifier*

Requirement	Optional
Description	Unique identifier of the competent authority. Shall be filled in with the unique code of the competent authority. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the data type <i>CompetentAuthorityDetails</i> (<i>competentAuthorityId_identifier</i>).
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	CA_AT_00_7

5.7.2 Field *competentAuthorityType*

Requirement	Optional
Description	Quiet area type for which the competent authority is responsible.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Link
Format	Only one value is allowed
Code list	Code list URL: https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/inspire/SpecialisedZoneTypeCode Applicable code list values: - quietAreaInAgglomeration - quietAreaInOpenCountry
Example	quietAreaInAgglomeration

5.7.3 Field quietAreaIdIdentifier

Requirement	Optional
Description	Unique identifier of the quiet area. It is expected to be the same as the identifier from the feature type QuietArea (quietAreaId_identifier) of the data schema Quiet area (DF7_10) from the dataflow Noise Action Plan (DF7_10).
Reportnet type	3.0 Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Example	QA_DK_00_1

5.8 Table ESTATUnitReference

The table *ESTATUnitReference* provides reference information concerning NUTS or LAU data if the Reporting level of the competent authorities is provided through those EUROSTAT classification of territorial units.

Table 5.7. *ESTATUnitReference* table overview

Mandatory /optional/ conditional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type	Code list
C	ESTATNUTSReferenceTitle	Text	
C	ESTATNUTSReferenceLink	URL	
C	ESTATLAUReferenceTitle	Text	
C	ESTATLAUReferenceLink	URL	

The following section includes detailed information of each field, i.e. description, type, format, use of code lists (where applicable), additional information of expected data or guidelines to prepare data, and data samples.

5.8.1 Field ESTATNUTSReferenceTitle

Requirement	Optional and conditional
Description	Version of the NUTS data used for the noise data reporting.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	Needs to be reported if competent authority is specified at NUTS level.
Example	ESTATNUTSReferenceTitle NUTS 2021, Version date: 01/02/2020, Scale: 1:1M, Source: Eurostat

5.8.2 Field *ESTATNUTSReferenceLink*

Requirement	Optional and conditional
Description	Link to the NUTS data used for the noise data reporting.
Reportnet 3.0 type	URL
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	Needs to be reported if competent authority is specified at NUTS level.
Example	https://gisco-services.ec.europa.eu/distribution/v2/nuts/download/ref-nuts-2021-01m.shp.zip

5.8.3 Field *ESTATLAUReferenceTitle*

Requirement	Optional and conditional
Description	Version of the LAU data used for the noise data reporting.
Reportnet 3.0 type	Text
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	Needs to be reported if competent authority is specified at LAU level.
Example	EUROSTAT Local Administrative Units (LAU), 2020

5.8.4 Field *ESTATLAUReferenceLink*

Requirement	Optional and conditional
Description	Link to the LAU data used for the noise data reporting.
Reportnet 3.0 type	URL
Format	Maximum of 10000 characters
Information	Needs to be reported if competent authority is specified at LAU level.
Example	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/lau

5.9 Table *DatasetDefaultProperties*

This table includes all properties that can have a default value in a data set. Typically, it includes: default values or void reason for voidable attributes defined in the INSPIRE specifications, and default values of other attributes. The table is prefilled and read-only.

Table 5.8. DatasetDefaultProperties table overview

Mandatory /optional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type
M	tableName	Text
M	propertyName	Text
O	attribute	Text
M	defaultValue	Text

Table 5.9. Applicable values for the DatasetDefaultProperties

tableName	propertyName	attribute	defaultValue
CompetentAuthorityDetails	competentAuthorityId_identifierScheme		http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/inspire/IdIdentifierScheme/EUENDCode

5.10 Table CodelistProperties

This table includes a list of the code lists that have to be used for reporting data on the DF2 Competent Authorities data model. The complete code lists used in the END data model are also published in the Eionet Data Dictionary (<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularies>) and are used in the Reportnet 3 data schemas.

The specific applicable code lists can also be found in the Vocabulary – common tables data schema of this dataflow.

The table is prefilled and read-only.

Table 5.10. CodelistProperties table overview

Mandatory /optional	Name	Reportnet 3.0 Type
M	tableName	Text
M	propertyName	Text
M	codelist	Text

Table 5.11. Applicable values for the CodelistProperties

tableName	propertyName	codelist
CompetentAuthorityAirport	competentAuthorityRole	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration	competentAuthoritySource	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/NoiseSourceValue
CompetentAuthorityAgglomeration	competentAuthorityRole	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
CompetentAuthorityRoad	competentAuthorityRole	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
CompetentAuthorityRoad	reportingLevel	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/LevelValue
CompetentAuthorityRail	competentAuthorityRole	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/CompetentAuthorityRoleValue
CompetentAuthorityRail	reportingLevel	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/noise/LevelValue
CompetentAuthorityQuietArea	competentAuthorityType	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/inspire/SpecialisedZoneTypeCode

5.11 Validation

The relevant information in relation to validation of this data schema is described in 3.1.

Two types of quality controls will be implemented:

- Quality controls in relation to consistency of reported data in DF2
- Cross checks between data reported in DF2 and data reported in DF1_5.

6 Cross checks between DF2 and DF1_5

This section will be updated after the first testing of DF2 in Reportnet 3.

7 Reporting process

7.1 Reporting data in Reportnet 3.0: overall workflow

Figure 7.1 illustrates the different processes involved in the reporting of DF2 Competent Authorities. The direct link to access all available supporting material of the noise reporting data flows can be found here: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise>. The preparation of the data involves using predefined templates in MS Excel with the competent authorities' information related to major roads, major railways, major airports and agglomerations. The dataflow is comprised by one data schema with different tables that need to be filled in. An MS Excel template is available for the data schema. One data schema will need to be uploaded, and once the file has been uploaded, it can be assessed based on the quality assurance validations that are programmed inside Reportnet 3. The description of these quality checks can be downloaded from: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/validation-rules_as_a_support_information_to_prepare_reporting_data. The latest validation rules are provided within the Reportnet 3 Info schema (Data flow help) of the reporting data flow.

Once the data is correct, without any blocking errors in the quality checks, the delivery can be completed by releasing the data collection. In case of blocking errors in the validation, the data cannot be released and the reporter will need to correct the content, replace the files and release the data collection again. After the data has been released, a confirmation receipt will be issued and will be available in the dataflow page. The data submitted will be available in Reportnet 3 and if there are other errors, you will receive a standard notification that a correction and a resubmission is needed. All the submissions will be integrated in the EU noise database.

Figure 7.1. Reporting workflow

Further information on the reporting process of DF2

- Reportnet 3 reporters' manual : https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/prod/reporter_howto_reportnet3.0
- Training video: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/reportnet/docs/noise/videos>

7.2 User accounts and permissions

The official reporting will be done through the following URL: <https://reportnet.europa.eu/>. The log in will be done through the EU login portal and the reporter will have to use the EU login details. Therefore, reporters will not be managing an Eionet login account, but they will use an EU login account which is separately maintained and that can be more easily updated. Creating an EU account can be done at <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/cas/about.html>.

Figure 7.2. Log in into Reportnet 3.0 using EU-login

In Reportnet 3.0 there are two main roles for reporters, one is the lead reporter's role and the other is the supporting reporter's role. Prior, in Reportnet 2, all reporters were registered by the EEA and the lists were maintained by the agency. In the new reporting mechanism, the supporting reporters can prepare the data and can access the reporting platform. The number of supporting reporters is unlimited but those will be managed by the lead reporter. The lead reporter will be in charge to submit the final data and needs to be formally nominated.

Figure 7.3. Roles in Reportnet 3.0

7.3 Importing data

To import the MS excel file, the custom imports (.xlsm, .xlsx) needs to be selected as indicated in Figure 7.4. The reporter will be asked to select a file and upload it. If the reporter is replacing the existing data, *Replace data* can be selected (see

Figure 7.5). The option **Replace data** will delete all previously imported data in all tables, which is particularly important if different reporters will import data for the same data schema.

Figure 7.4. Import dataset data

Figure 7.5. Replace data

7.4 Validations

The data to be submitted can be assessed with the validation tools provided in Reportnet 3.0 as shown in Figure 7.6.

Figure 7.6. Show validations

The validations are run automatically when the data is uploaded, and the reports can be consulted as shown in Figure 7.7.

Figure 7.7. Validations report

Entity	Table	Field	Code	Level error	Message	Number of records
RECORD	CompetentAuthorityRoad		TU68	ERROR	Uniqueness and multiplicity constraints - The fields competentAuthorityIdIdentifier, competentAuthorityRole, reportingLevel and ESTATUnitCode are uniques within table	2
FIELD	CompetentAuthorityDetails	competentAuthorityIdIdentifier	CF7	WARNING	CF7: The [competentAuthorityIdIdentifier] value doesn't follow the requested code formation	2
FIELD	CompetentAuthorityDetails	competentAuthorityName	FC52	BLOCKER	The value must not be missing or empty	4
RECORD	CompetentAuthorityRoad		TU91	ERROR	Uniqueness and multiplicity constraints - The fields competentAuthorityIdIdentifier, competentAuthorityRole and reportingLevel are uniques within table	2
TABLE	CompetentAuthorityAirport		RT2	BLOCKER	RT2: Mismatching [competentAuthorityIdIdentifier] values between CompetentAuthorityAirport and CompetentAuthorityDetails (OMISSION)	1
RECORD	CompetentAuthorityRail		TU77	ERROR	Uniqueness and multiplicity constraints - either one field or combination of fields are unique within table	2

If there are no blockers, errors, warnings, or information messages in the data uploaded, the message shown in Figure 7.8 will be given. Errors identified as “blockers” will not allow the reporter to release the data collection. Obtaining blockers in the validation process means that the data delivered has missing or erroneous elements that may corrupt the integrity of the European noise database or undermine the consistency of the reported data.

All quality control rules are described in Dataflow Help - Dataset schemas / QC rules (see chapter 3.1).

Figure 7.8. Successful validation message

7.5 Official submission of the report

The reporter will be able to submit the data by clicking on "Release to data collection" as shown in Figure 7.9. If there are blockers in any dataset schema, the release will be stopped and the reporter will receive a message indicating that releasing the data is not possible due to errors in the dataset. The reporter can make copies of the data submitted. After the submission a new icon will appear with the confirmation receipt as shown in Figure 7.10. The confirmation receipt is a pdf with a confirmation of the submission which indicates the data schemas that were submitted. If the reporter changes the

data and resubmits a new copy to the data collection, then a new confirmation receipt will be available for download.

Figure 7.9. Release data collection

Figure 7.10. Confirmation receipt

7.6 Submission and resubmission

DF2 must be submitted in Reportnet 3 anytime between the submission of DF1_5 and the submission of DF7_10. The reporter will be able to replace/update the submission at any time between the submission of DF1_5 and the submission of DF7_10.

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The European Topic Centre on Air pollution,
transport, noise and industrial pollution (ETC/ATNI)
is a consortium of European institutes under a
framework partnership contract to the European
Environment Agency.

